

Election Governance Based on Public Participation in Indonesia

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Abstract

This article discusses election governance based on public participation with qualitative research methods, the approach used in case studies in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province, the region is one of thirty-four province in Indonesia. Governance is an approach that is considered relevant, because election governance is its manifestation. The results show that the Regional of General Election Commission of NTB as the authority of election organizers succeeded in building a model of election governance based on public participation through three strategies, namely the movement to protect suffrage, family-based voter education, and voter education based on educational institutions. These three models are designed through three approaches, namely multi-stakeholder partnership, convergence, safety and public health of disaster areas. The methods of implementation include; short videos about elections, consistent use of mass media and continuous election classes. The impact of the public participation-based election governance model in NTB is that the number of public participation in 2019 Elections increased to 82 percent compared to 2014 Election of 77.32 percent where the model has not been implemented. The obstacles faced in building participatory-based election governance are two, namely; the issue of legitimacy provided by the Electoral Law and has not been made the education of voters as core business of General Commission Election, while voter education is an effective instrument in developing public participation. The solution is necessary to change article 3 and article 15 (Presiden Republik Indonesia, 2017) on the elections to include participation as the principle of organizing elections. In addition, voter education should be the core business from the national to the regions.

Introduction

Elections as a process of peaceful circulation of political leaders as well as a means of implementing people's sovereignty should be organized through democratic mechanisms. In the sense of implementing the principles of *good governance*, which is none other than the system or way of managing elections pursued by election organizers who are expected to comply with the principles of participatory, consensus-oriented, accountable, transparency, responsive, effective and efficient, fair, inclusive, and follow the rule of law (Sheng, 2010). Participation as a model of *good governance* bases on (Sheng, 2010) in Indonesia has not been regulated as good governance in the principle of organizing elections, while according to (Zutshi, 2014) participation is the basis of democratic election governance.

The Constitution of Indonesia Republic in 1945 and Presiden Republik Indonesia (2017) about The General Election does mention the principle of Elections is direct, general, free, confidential, honest, and fair. The problem is that the direct principle cannot be categorized as the principle of *good governance* because it explains the community's autonomy in using their suffrage that is not through representation. *Good governance* on the other hand is a working guideline for public authorities, such as organizers in the implementation of elections.

Elections in Indonesia still require governance based on public participation, because the constitution places voting in elections is a public right not an obligation. Consequently, the state cannot force every citizen to vote in every election. In fact, in quantity, public participation to vote is still high. For example, in the implementation of elections in 2019, election participation in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province is above the national participation average. Table 1 below shows the evidence.

Table 1: Voter Participations Rate of the Election in 2019 in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB)

No.	Voter Levels	Participations	
		National	West Nusa Tenggara (NTB)
1.	House Representatives	81,69	82,77

2.	Regional Representative Councils	82,15	82,2
3.	President and Vice President	81,97	82,91

Source: General Election Commission of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province and (Indonesia, 2019)

Table 1 above describes election participation in NTB of 82.77% for the Election of members of the House of Representatives (DPR), 82.8% for the election of members of the Regional Representative Councils (DPD), and 82.91 percent for the Presidential and Vice Presidential Elections General Election Commission of NTB in 2019. National participation for presidential and Vice Presidential elections is 81.97%, House of Representatives elections are 81.69%, and Regional Representative Councils voters are 82.15%. Election Participation in NTB also shows consistency at each level of elections such as House of Representatives, Regional Representative Councils, President and Vice President (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2020). This means that there is a significant increase in voter participation rate compared to the 2014 election of 77.32% (General Election Commission of NTB Province, 2014). Even in 2015 regional head elections had shown alarming participation rates, for example in Mataram City as one of the cities in NTB, which was 56.94% (WINENGAN, 2018).

It is interesting to examine how to build effective public participation so that such a high level of participation can be achieved. High public participation in choosing as shown by the data above is one indication of the capacity of KPUD of NTB. They take a role, as an Election's authority in the region is quite good in the innovation of *good governance* implementation in the field of election governance, especially in encouraging the principle of participation. Based on the description above, it is necessary to explore the governance strategy of elections based on public participation in NTB as a representation phenomenon of organizing elections in Indonesia.

Previous Research

The implementation of *good governance* in election governance is a phenomenon that has become a concern in a number of countries. Elections that are not held properly will result in weak legitimacy of the government. The case of the presidential election in Afghanistan in 2009 for example showed the weak capacity of election organizers in preventing widespread fraud during the election process has resulted in a decrease in public confidence in the governance Election (Berman, et. al., 2019). During the election process, the public experienced their own cheating of organizers and the intervention of politicians against the organizers. Election fraud has occurred from the storage of ballot boxes, counting of votes, to recapitulation of votes at the provincial and national levels. The end of the public's lack of trust in electoral governance led to low voter participation and their trust in government was poor.

One of the principles of *good governance* that is widely highlighted to influence quality of election governance is the independence of the organizing body. The public believes in an Election organized by an independent governing body from political intervention, so that the democratic countries of the world tend to choose the model of an independent organizing organization (Rosas, 2010). Nigerian citizens for example are more concerned with the political autonomy of the election organizing body and more forgiving of procedural errors stemming from the lack capacity of the election organizing body (Kerr, 2013).

The importance of the efficacy of election organizers to get results that elections have high legitimacy is also shown by some research, such as Pasaribu (2019), and Faiz (2018), as well as International & IDEA (2012). Pasaribu (2019) mentions that the determining factor of the level of legitimacy and credibility of an election organizing body are its independence. Referring to the perspective of further legal science (Pasaribu, 2019), the equivalent of the word independent is independent. Sardini (2018) complemented that view by stating that there are fifteen aspects of democratic election governance, one of which is the independence of the organizing body. While International & IDEA (2012) believe in the existence of independent organizing bodies as a way of building voter confidence in the fair Election process.

Another issue that supports the quality of election governance is the organization's capacity to innovate the implementation of *good governance*. Transparency of Election governance in the era of industrialization using Communication Information Technology (ICT) for example has proven effective in building public trust in elections (King & Youngblood, 2016). Their findings were supported by Tanaamah, Hastari & Tanaem (2019) who showed the results of their research, namely KPU Nomination Information System (SILON) in Indonesia in 2019 elections has a contribution to transparency of election governance, especially improving the *performance* of the organizing body organization (2019).

In short, all of the above research has given awareness that the independence of election organizers and the implementation of *good governance* in election governance is a need for democratic election governance. The problem is, although the concept of governance, and *good governance* has been worldwide, there has been

no research that specifically finds the model of election governance based on public participation as one of the important public values. These findings have urgency for election governance, which is facing the challenges of increasingly apathetic public behavior in elections. This paper is trying to fill the void by presenting the best experience (*best practice*) the KPUD of NTB in election governance based on public participation. It wishes that the *best practice* of KPUD NTB Province would inspire the governance elections in various regions or other countries.

Government Management Structure

The concept of governance comes from the Greek "*kubernao*", meaning directing. The word "*kubernao*", passed on in Latin to "*gubernare*" and eventually spun by many other languages (Addink, 2018). Initially the concept of *governance* came from the thinking of African scholars who were inspired by their concerns about the *governance* crisis in the country concerned. African scholars understand *governance* as a pattern of relations between countries and communities in the frame of democracy and inclusiveness (Susanto, 2019). The concept of *governance* is also understood as a differentiator with the *government* began to be popularized by the World Bank in 1989 (Pratikno, 2005). Between *government* and *governance*, have fundamental differences, as presented through table 2.

Table 2: The Different between *Government* and *Governance*

No	Comparison Element	Government	Governance
1.	Meaning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration process by authorized institutions • Institutions that organize government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of government administration • Management of government administration • Governance
2.	Relational Characteristic	Hierarchical, in the sense that the ruling is above, while the citizens ruled are low	Hierarchical in the sense that there is equality and only being in function
3.	Components Involved	The subject is only one government institution	There are three components involved, namely the public, private, and public sectors

Source: (Sinaga, 2017; Susanto, 2019)

Table 2 above shows that *governance* is an inclusive concept, while *government* is more exclusive. It is called exclusive because the concept of *government* positioning the government tends to close itself, keeping distance from citizens, even at some point being dictatorial in the formulation and implementation of public policy. Instead, *governance* opens up, does not keep its distance from citizens and submits policy implementation in the political, economic, and social fields to non-governmental organizations. All exposure to expert opinion above confirms the concept of *governance* as governance that involves as many *stakeholders* as possible in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public policy.

Governance is carried out with a number of models, and each model offers a different emphasis. Ikeanyibe, Eze Ori & Okoye (2017) are dividing into four *governance* models, including government as a government; *good governance*; *governance* as a good enough government; collaboration, partnership, or network governance. Ideally, *good governance* focuses on compiling various models, such as compiling *good governance* and collaboration models. The compilation model is very relevant in election governance because both are a unified function in the governance of democratic elections. Other scholars understand *good governance* as a government that prevents corruption, respect for the law, transparency, participation, efficient, effective, accountability, and orderly (Beetseh, 2014; Guy, 2010; Widjajanti & Sugiyanto, 2015). The conception of *good governance* is the reason why World Bank directs the development of *good governance* in developing countries through the improvement of government capacity.

The views of the scholars above help the formulation concept of *good governance* as the implementation of the *good governance* values, including [governance](#), which is free from corruption, collusion

and nepotism, adherence to legal guidelines, responsiveness, administrative order, respect for the rights of every citizen and provide equality in service, transparent, effective, efficient, accountable, and no less important is to encourage public participation. These values are universal and applicable to all types of organizations, but *good governance* has been synonymous with the governance of public organizations. Although the concept of *good governance* has been, exist in the world, but the indicators of its implementation are still diverse. The following are shown examples of *good governance* indicators according to a number of sources.

Table 3: Good Governance Indicators

No	(UNDP, 2016)	(World Dev. Indic. 1998, 1998)	(Presiden Republik Indonesia, 2017)
1.	Participation	Transparency	Independent
2.	Legal Certainty	Integrity	Trusty
3.	Transparency	Accountability	Fair
4.	Responsiveness	Responsibility	Legal Certainty
5.	Consensus	Participation	Orderly
6.	Equality		Openly
7.	Affectivity		Proportional
8.	Efficiency		Professional
9.	Accountability		Accountable
10.	Strategic		Effective and Efficiency

Source: managed from various sources

Table 3 above shows the pioneers of *good governance* concept in developing countries such as the United Nation Development Programmed (UNDP) and the World Bank including participation as an indicator of good governance. UNDP includes ten indicators of *good governance* such as participation, legal certainty, transparency, responses, consensus, equality, effectiveness, efficiency, accountability, and strategic. The World Bank includes five indicators: transparency, integrity, accountability, responsibility, and participation. *Good governance* in the governance of elections in Indonesia regulated through the election law includes ten indicators, namely independent, honest, fair, legal, orderly, open (transparency), proportional, professional, accountable, effective and efficient. Participation included by UNDP and the World Bank has not been included as an indicator of *good governance* in election governance in Indonesia.

Election Management

Election Governance is a study of the role exercised by the Electoral authority, as well as how the Electoral authority performs its role to ensure the successful implementation of elections. Two terms used to describe the electoral authority are the Election Organizing Body and the Election Organizing Body (LPP). Both have the same meaning, therefore this article uses both terms alternately.

The election governance process covers three scopes including; establishment of body or regulatory bodies and norms, implementation of these norms, as well as dispute resolution (Torres & Díaz, 2015). Election norms can be divided into two levels, namely arrangements related to competition and organizing. Both levels have sub-levels as well as table 4 below.

Table 4: Election Governance Settings

No	Setting Levels	Sublevel Setting
1.	Competency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of constituencies • Allocation of seats in each constituency • How to convert sound into seats
2.	Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to register and verify the party • How to register voters • How to register and verify candidates • Financing or budget • How to build voter participation • How to monitor • How to supervise • Recapitulation of election results

Source: (Torres & Díaz, 2015)

Torres & Díaz (2015) model above shows a study on elections covering two groups, namely the *electoral system* and *electoral governance*. The *electoral system* deals with the choice of the division of constituencies, the allocation of seats of each constituency, and the way the vote is converted into seats. These three sections are the competition areas of election participants. Because of its nature of political competition, studies of the area are widely carried out by political science scholars. *Electoral governance* concerns how the

electoral administration agency or the KPU carries out the implementation of elections. *Electoral governance* is closer to the functions of public services, including registration and verification of political parties of prospective election participants, voter registration, registration and verification of candidates, financing or budget, building voter participation, monitoring elections, monitoring elections, and recapitulation of election results. Based on the conception of election governance, which is a slice of the function of public services, strong enough to mention the governance elections is a study area of public administration that is a variant of the *governance* paradigm.

Electoral governance is adopted from the concept of *governance*, and its application in elections is interpreted as not only *electoral governance amounts to much more than just administration* but also as an instrument to measure the assessment of whether the conduct of a country's elections is in accordance with the principles of good governance. It because election activities are part of government activities with the aim of achieving or maintaining the credibility of elections in democratic countries. The evidence that develops among public administration scholars including political science scholars is the implementations of elections that apply the principles of good governance ensure the stages process, election results, and election organizers integrities (Mozaffar & Schedler, 2002).

Research Method

This research is a qualitative research of case studies that refers to John W. Creswell, (2013). One of the reasons for the selection of case studies are the focus of this research is the implementation of public participation in the governance Elections 2019 in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB). The *focus* of this research is in line with (Creswell, 2013) assertion that case study research was designed for researches related to evaluation, by developing in-depth analysis of a program or process. This research is related to the evaluation of election governance based on public participation in 2019 in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province.

Result And Discussion

Indonesia has an institutional election organizer that is divided into three powers, namely KPU, General Election Supervisory Board (Bawaslu), and General Election Organizing Council (DKPP). KPU is the main administrator of election governance who is authorized to plan and implement the election stage. The supervisory function of the stage implementation is given to General Election Supervisory Board (Bawaslu), and only the function of handling the organizer's code of conduct is given to General Election Organizing Council (DKPP).

It is said to be the main administrator because only KPU is mentioned directly in the Constitution of the Indonesia Republic in 1945. Article 22E stated that an electoral commission with a national, permanent, and independent nature organizes election. The national word indicates the organization of KPU consists of three levels in hierarchy, namely the national KPU, Provincial KPU, and District/City KPU. The word still has the meaning that the nature of KPU organization is permanent. Independency is interpreted as a model of KPU organization that is free from political intervention in the exercise of its authority. KPU institutional designed that thus strengthens the research results (International & IDEA, 2012; Kerr, 2013; Pasaribu, 2019; Rosas, 2010). Referring to the data and thoughts above, Indonesia is a country that adheres to the model of independent election organizing bodies from the national to regional levels that have been practiced since 2004.

The policy of simultaneous election governance in 2019 was the election members of DPR, Regional DPD, President and Vice President, DPRD constructed in ten stages. They are classified such as follows: (1) program and budget planning and technical regulations; (2) updating voter data and drafting voter lists; (3) registration and verification of election participants; (4) determination of election participants; (5) the number of seats and constituencies determinations. (6) The nomination of President and Vice President, DPR, DPD, DPRD Province, and DPRD District/City; (7) Election campaign; (8) quiet period; (9) voting and counting of votes; and (10) determination of election results.

Election norms mentions the implementation of all the above stages, based on eleven principles of governance that include; independent, honest, fair, legal, orderly, open, proportionate, accountable, effective, and efficient. This principle generally meets the requirements of *good governance* norms in the perspective of (Sheng, 2010; UNDP, 2016; *World Dev. Indic. 1998, 1998*). The disadvantage is that the governance principles of the organization have not included the participation as well as good governance principles as the idea of (UNDP, 2016; *World Dev. Indic. 1998, 1998*). In addition, the inclusion of participation shows that the principles of governance elections in Indonesia have not been in line with (Bupinder Zutshi, 2014) stated that the principle of public participation is the main principle as well as the basis of democratic election governance.

The lack norm about public participation does not decrease the motivation of KPU in encouraging participatory election governance. This phenomenon is related to the *design* of the implementation of elections that looking for to include voter socialization or education programs as well as the existence of community participation parts or divisions in the organizational structure of KPU of West NTB (2020). Both facts are

manifestations of the commitment and strong vision of KPU of NTB to do more than just as implementers of election norms are during 2019 election process. Public participation has even been included in a nomenclature called voter participation, which can be interpreted as a sign that public participation is a program of continuous work in the institution of KPU of NTB. This model succeeded in increasing the public participation rate above the national participation average, although it is recognized not to be the only variable that gives birth to high voter participation, but also in terms of the process KPU of NTB has innovated election governance based on public participation.

Public participation policy is implemented through voter socialization and education activities aimed at building public knowledge and skills on how the 2019 Concurrent Election system works and placing election integrity as a guideline for voter behavior in the exercise of their political rights. The expected *outcome* policy is for voters not only to participate in the Electorate but also to be skilled in using their voting rights to reduce invalid ballots. The high number of invalid ballots makes public participation in elections less meaningful because it cannot be converted into the votes of election participants.

Implementation of election governance policy based on public participation is practiced through three strategies: the movement to protect suffrage; socialization and education of family-based voters; and socialization and education of voters based on educational institutions. The movement to protect suffrage is carried out through cooperation with local governments. Implementation of this program is the administration of voter data based on Electronic Resident ID Card (E-KTP) through the application <http://lindungihakpilihmu.kpu.go.id> or by downloaded from *Play Store* <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details>. The policy helps people check their names on voter lists through their homes or workplaces, making it easier for political parties and prospective lawmakers to check their constituents whether or not they are registered on the voter list, making it easier for them to plan data-driven electoral work.

Socialization and education of family-based voters becomes a participatory election governance strategy that is seen as effective in building the quality of elections. As a result, families as the smallest social institutions are seen as still effective in instilling individual integrity such as honesty, fairness, not cheating, and peace loving. These norms are a need in building an election governance order with integrity as one of the indicators of the elections quality.

Educational institutions are the second step that is seen as effective because in educational institutions there are novice voters who are a generation that is expected to be the vanguard of building the elections quality. According to data from the Draft KPU of NTB, from 3,667,523 total voters in NTB Province, the number of novice voters, i.e. people less than 20 years old on polling day or April 9, 2019 amounted to 337,830 people or 9.21% (2019:24). Although the number of novice voters is relatively small, but the attention of KPU of NTB to the segment is quite large, which can be seen from the large program of socialization and education of voters through visits to schools and universities, coupled with a smart race about elections.

There are four approaches practiced by KPU of NTB in election governance based on public participation. *First, multi-stakeholder partnership*, namely the involvement of *stakeholders* in all elections, it is including the socialization and education of voters. *Second*, convergence is to integrate methods in socializing and education of voters. *Third*, public safety and health in the era of natural and other disasters, namely the approach of public safety and health in every community participation program, especially in the era of disasters both natural disasters and non-natural disasters. *Fourth, objective data and research*, i.e. all community participation work relies on reset and objective data.

The methods of socialization and education voters who are believed to increase public participation in election governance vary. They consist of a short video about elections; consistent utilization of social media, print media, and electronic media; include the theme of Elections in the school education curriculum; voter segmentation; building election classes by maximizing the function of The Election Smart House (RPP) that is already in KPU of NTB.

The model of election governance based on public participation implemented by KPU of NTB strengthens the paradigm of *governance* in election governance. Following the ideas from (Ikeanyibe et al., 2017) especially concerning two ways of implementing *governance*, namely *good governance* and collaboration. The role of KPU of NTB at the same time proves this research proposition that participation as part of good governance and *multi-stakeholder* collaboration is a unified function in the governance of democratic elections, one of which is measured by the high participation rate of voters in elections.

The Capacity of KPU of NTB in election governance based on public participation while strengthening or supporting the results bases on research from (King & Youngblood, 2016; Tanaamah et al., 2019). This essence gives the message that the application of good governance in elections or *good electoral governance* can be done through various means. In addition to transparency, another way that isn't less important such as public participation, because elections are the most tangible implementation of public participation in the democratic system, in addition (Zutshi, 2014) mention it as a basis democracy.

Conclusion And Suggestion

The success of the West Nusa Tenggara Regional Election Commission in presenting election governance based on public participation has not gained juridical legitimacy from Presiden Republik Indonesia about the Election. This indication is evident from two facts. *First*, the inclusion of public participation as the principles of organizing elections stipulated in article 3 of this ACT. *Second*, continuous political education has not been the task of KPU set out in article 15. There is little opportunity for KPU Provincial to conduct a public participation program, namely article 15-letter j. However, the provisions in this article do not clearly give the task for KPU Provincial to conduct public participation policies, but only the assignment of socialization of elections. The implication is that after the election phase ends, KPU Provincial in the region has no obligation to implement a public participation program. The two facts above explain the design of election governance policy in Indonesia has not been in accordance with *good governance* standards based on the ideas of the World Bank and UNDP.

The commitment to build democracy is the motivation of KPU of NTB to implement public participation as a way of implementing the concept of *good governance* in the election sector. The strategy is through three program models, namely the movement to protect suffrage, socialization and education of family-based voters, as well as socialization and education of voters based on educational institutions. These three models are innovations from KPU of NTB Province and have an impact on increasing the voter participation rate to reach 82.77% for DPR member elections, 82.8% for the Election of DPD members, and 82.91% for the Presidential and Vice Presidential Elections. This figure is higher than the 2014 General Election, which reached 77.32%. It should be given an appreciation for the capacity of KPU of NTB in carrying out the roles of public participation.

Recommendations worth offering are the need to strengthen the governance capacity of elections based on public participation through revisions relate to two articles, namely article 3 and article 15. The provisions in article 3 should regulate public participation as the principle of organizing elections as well as the principles of good governance. The provision of article 15 should add the task of KPU from national to regional is to carry out voter education, so that KPU *business core* not only carry out the election stage but also carry out voter education. The urgency, to give the legality of the implementation of public participation programs as a way to improve the elections quality that are the basic needs of electoral democracy.

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